

Cooling of Neutron Stars by Neutrino Emission

Burak Cem Coşkun¹

¹*Gazi Ethem Paşa St. 8/4, 34742 Kadıköy, İstanbul, Türkiye**

(Dated: March 21, 2025)

We present two major neutrino cooling mechanisms and the corresponding energy outputs (i.e. luminosities) in the inner crust and the core. The one is the electron-nucleus bremsstrahlung which happens in the crust and the other is Urca process occurring at high densities. We investigate density dependence of the neutrino emissivities at various temperatures, partial emissivities due to electron-nucleus bremsstrahlung (e-brems), and the total emissivity produced by direct and modified Urca processes.

I. COOLING PROCESSES BY NEUTRINO EMISSION

Neutron stars are believed to be formed in very high internal temperatures, $T > 10^{11}$ K, in the center of supernova explosions. After the supernova explosion, internal temperature initially drops to 10^9 K with powerful neutrino emission mechanisms while the crust stays hot. The cooling wave propagates to the crust and the neutrino emission dominates at least for 1000 years. Photon emission takes over only when the internal temperature falls to 10^8 K. Calculations of the thermal evolution of the star is very sensitive to the state of matter [1] [2]. The most important quantity for the thermal evolution of neutron stars is the *neutrino emissivity* Q (energy carried away by neutrinos and anti-neutrinos per second per unit volume). The direct calculations of emissivity are based on the Weinberg-Salam-Glashow theory of electroweak interactions [3]. In this section we will describe two main neutrino cooling mechanisms and the corresponding energy outputs (i.e. luminosities) in the inner crust and the core. The first one is the electron-nucleus bremsstrahlung which happens in the crust and the other is Urca process with nucleons occurring at high densities.

A. Electron-nucleus bremsstrahlung

In the case of zero magnetic field, the bremsstrahlung process dominates in denser layers of the crust at not very high temperatures, $T < 10^9$ K (at which the nuclei are not dissociated). Here, bremsstrahlung means neutrino emission due to electromagnetic interaction of electrons with atomic nuclei [4]. The Coulomb scattering of electrons by atomic nuclei in a Coulomb liquid or crystal can be written schematically as

$$e + (Z, A) \rightarrow e + (Z, A) + \nu + \bar{\nu}. \quad (1)$$

It proceeds via neutral and charged electroweak currents and leads to emission of neutrinos of all flavors. The

energy output for this process is estimated to be

$$L_{\nu}^{brem} \simeq (5 \times 10^{39} \text{ erg s}^{-1}) \left(\frac{M_{crust}}{M_{\odot}} \right) T_9^6, \quad (2)$$

where M_{crust} is the mass of the crust and T_9 is the temperature in the units of 10^9 K [3]. Each degenerate species contribute to the cooling rate, that is why we have the 6th power of T in Equation 2.

If we define crust thickness as $\Delta R_{crust} = R - R_{core}$, the volume of the crust becomes $4\pi R^2 \Delta R_{crust}$. So, using Equation 2 one can calculate the total emission rate, Q .

B. Urca processes

In [5], we have discussed the neutronization with inverse β decay and briefly mentioned its importance on the cooling of neutron stars with neutrino emissions. Combined direct and inverse β reaction is called Urca (*Unrecorded Cooling Agent*) process. These reactions are much slower than inter-particle collisions in matter. At very high temperatures $T > 10^9$ K Urca process is the dominant energy loss mechanism. These reactions are schematically written as

$$n \rightarrow p + e + \bar{\nu}_i, \quad (3)$$

$$e + p \rightarrow n + \nu_i. \quad (4)$$

Here i refers to different flavors such as electron, muon and tau neutrinos. These reactions are also called the *direct* Urca process and can occur only if the proton concentration is sufficiently high (see [5]). If we consider a possible neutron decay as it is given in Equation 3, the Fermi momenta satisfy the relation $p_F(e) = p_F(p) \ll p_F(n)$. It is then not possible to satisfy the conservation of momentum. In order to satisfy this condition, another particle must be present to absorb momentum. So, we have *modified* Urca reactions as follows

$$n + n \rightarrow n + p + e + \bar{\nu}_i, \quad (5)$$

$$n + p + e \rightarrow n + n + \nu_i. \quad (6)$$

Muon neutrino emitting reactions occur near nuclear densities, $\rho \geq 8 \times 10^{14} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$.

* coskunburak@itu.edu.tr; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7779-8378>

FIG. 1: Density dependence of the neutrino emissivities at various temperatures and partial emissivities due to electron-nucleus bremsstrahlung (e-brems) and the total emissivity produced by direct and modified Urca processes.

For a neutron star with uniform density ρ and mass M , the energy output for the Urca process is

$$L_{\nu}^{Urca} \simeq (8.5 \times 10^{38} \text{ erg s}^{-1}) \left(\frac{M}{M_{\odot}} \right) \left(\frac{\rho_{nuc}}{\rho} \right)^{1/3} T_9^8 (1 + F), \quad (7)$$

where $\rho_{nuc} = 2.8 \times 10^{14} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ and F is the energy loss rate resulted from the appearance of muon neutrinos, ν_{μ}

instead of electron neutrinos, ν_e . Energy loss rate is given as

$$F = \begin{cases} 0, & \rho \leq 2.9\rho_{nuc} \\ \left\{ 1 - \left(\frac{m_{\mu}c^2}{E_F(e)} \right)^2 \right\}^{1/2}, & \rho \geq 2.9\rho_{nuc} \end{cases}, \quad (8)$$

Neutrino emissivities at various temperatures for these processes are presented in Figure 1, basic neutron star models are used for the calculations [6] [7].

II. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSIONS

In § I, some of the beta processes are discussed as sources of cooling by neutrino emission in early stages of a neutron star's life. Neutrino scattering processes, may well exhibit the diffractive effects depending on the geometry of the nuclei. Since the neutrino wave numbers are of order 0.1 to 0.5 fm⁻¹, and the widths of the one-dimensional slabs (in the lasagna phase) are of order 10 fm, the diffraction criteria is satisfied [8]. Throughout our work in [5] we investigate the density profiles for exotic nuclei. The presence of nonspherical nuclei might accelerate the cooling of the corresponding region of neutron stars by opening semileptonic weak processes which

does not occur for spherical nuclei [9]. Furthermore, due to the continuous proton spectrum at the Fermi surface in the elongated direction, the direct URCA processes might occur faster.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work is based mainly on the Bachelor's thesis of BCC, "Physics of Neutron Star Crusts", submitted to the Department of Physics Engineering at Istanbul Technical University and supervised by K. Yavuz Ekşi in 2017.

-
- [1] D. Page, U. Geppert, and F. Weber, *Nuclear Physics A* **777**, 497 (2006).
 - [2] D. G. Yakovlev, A. D. Kaminker, O. Y. Gnedin, and P. Haensel, **354**, 1 (2001), astro-ph/0012122.
 - [3] S. L. Shapiro and S. A. Teukolsky, *Black Holes, White Dwarfs, and Neutron Stars: the Physics of Compact Objects* (John Wiley, 1983).
 - [4] A. D. Kaminker, C. J. Pethick, A. Y. Potekhin, V. Thorsson, and D. G. Yakovlev, **343**, 1009 (1999), astro-ph/9812447.
 - [5] B. C. Coşkun (2017), unpublished thesis, Istanbul Technical University.
 - [6] O. Y. Gnedin, D. G. Yakovlev, and A. Y. Potekhin, **324**, 725 (2001), astro-ph/0012306.
 - [7] See Table I.
 - [8] D. G. Ravenhall, C. J. Pethick, and J. R. Wilson, *Physical Review Letters* **50**, 2066 (1983).
 - [9] C. P. Lorenz, D. G. Ravenhall, and C. J. Pethick, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **70**, 379 (1993).

Appendix A: Tables

TABLE I: Neutron star models

$M [M_{\odot}]$	R [km]	$\rho_c [10^{14} \text{ g cm}^{-3}]$	$M_{crust} [M_{\odot}]$	ΔR_{crust} [km]
1.1	12.20	8.50	0.050	1.66
1.2	12.04	9.52	0.044	1.45
1.3	11.86	10.70	0.039	1.26
1.4	11.65	12.20	0.033	1.09